

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS ON FRICTION EFFECTS IN 4ENF FRACTURE TESTS

S. Stutz , J. Cugnoni , J. Botsis *

Laboratory of Applied Mechanics and Reliability Analysis, EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland

* Corresponding author (john.botsis@epfl.ch)

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Abstract

The effects of friction on the load-displacement response and the energy release rate (ERR) are examined in Mode II delamination. Uniaxial carbon-epoxy specimens are prepared and tested using the four end notch flexure (4ENF) test configuration. In selected specimens, optical fibers with several Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are embedded during the specimen fabrication, one layer above the delamination plane, to extract strain data during crack propagation. Two types of supports are used to examine the effects of friction: pin set-up and a roller set-up. The later type indicates a negligible influence while the former indicates a strong influence on the load displacement curves, the strain data recorded by the sensors and the ERR. The experimental data suggest a negligible bridging in the wake of the crack. The strain data are used to identify the model parameters including damage initiation and ERR as well as friction parameters. The numerical model with the identified parameters reproduced very well the experimental curves. The results of this work demonstrate that friction at the support plays an important role on the overall response of the specimen.

1. Introduction

It is well known that delamination is one of the most important failure modes of layered polymer composites. During delamination, crack bridging by intact fibers, matrix cracking, interface failure, fiber fracture, matrix yielding, friction of the crack planes, etc. may take place. The extent of any of the damage types depends on component geometry and loading conditions. To realistically model delamination growth, these processes need to be taken into account. Research in delamination in different polymeric layered materials considers formulations based on concepts of fracture mechanics (for a recent review

see ref [1]), initially developed for isotropic materials. These concepts have been extended to account for the anisotropy present in composites [2]. The ERR relation to the corresponding stress intensity factor (SIF) for each one of the three modes of fracture is defined in a similar manner to the isotropic cases but they are more complicated [2]. Nevertheless such relations have been proven very useful in characterizing fracture of anisotropic materials. In the last several years, numerical simulations and elements of damage mechanics have been used to model and predict delamination growth [3]. Such formulations are based on special elements ahead of the crack tip with typical stress - opening displacement relations which are either inferred from experimental-numerical data or assumed in the FE formulations.

Recently, Botsis and coworkers [4-6] reported experimental and numerical studies on delamination in uniaxial composite materials. Using strain data from embedded sensors on planes parallel to the delamination and inverse numerical modeling, they have carried identification of bridging tractions in Mode I delamination. These tractions were combined with a simple cohesive model to predict very well the load displacement curve of the DCB specimen [4,5].

While Mode I delamination testing using the DCB specimen has been well understood and characterized with the test procedures standardized [7], Mode II delamination testing has not reached the same level of understanding and a standard as in the case of Mode I has not yet emerged. While a few specimen geometries have been proposed in the literature [8,9] a realistic test is the four point end notch flexure specimen. However, several issues have not been completely resolved due to problems associated with the experimental set up, friction load application, etc.

In this paper, the effects of supports and the friction between the crack planes during delamination are investigated using a combined experimental-numerical approach. The four point end notched flexure test (4ENF) configuration is used to test uniaxial composite specimens. This configuration is chosen because it results in stable crack propagation. The supports of the specimen were changed so that the friction on those locations was minimized. In selected specimens optical fibers were embedded. These fibers contain eight sensors at 3 mm apart for quasi continuous strain measurements during delamination which help to locate the crack tip. In addition the strain measurements were used in conjunction with a parametric finite element (FE) model specially constructed to analyze the data of load displacement curves and examine the effects of friction on the overall delamination growth behavior.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials and specimens

The samples were produced in house by hand layup of the carbon epoxy prepreg material *SE 70* from *Gurit SP™*. The unidirectional composite plate with 20 layers was cured at 80°C for 8h under vacuum. The initial crack for the delamination tests was introduced with a 20 μm thick and 60mm long PTFE film placed between layers 10 and 11 (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: A schematic of the composite plate with the surrounding metallic frame and the sensor [5].

Beams of 25mm in width were cut from the cured composite plate. The beam's sides were sanded, sprayed white, and then marked every millimetre with a fine black ink pen to help monitoring the crack length. The material properties used in the numerical analysis were as follows: $E_{11} = 98$ GPa for the longitudinal modulus, measured in a three point bending test; $E_{22} = E_{33} = 9$ GPa for the transversal moduli, measured using standard uniaxial tests; $G = 5.2$ GPa was assumed for all shear moduli. The following Poisson ratios were measured $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$ and $\nu_{23} = 0.45$ was assumed. Selected samples were equipped (each one) with a single optical fiber (Fig. 1). They were placed during manufacturing

between layers 11 and 12 of the composite resulting in a distance of about 200 μm from the crack plane in the cured composite, as measured by optical microscopy on polished cross sections. Both ends of each optical fiber were guided to the base plate that was used for manufacturing through slits in a metal frame placed around the layup. At the exit points, they were fixed with adhesive tape to keep them in place during curing of the composite.

The optical fibers were single mode (i.e. SM28 with 125/9 μm fiber to core diameter ratio) with 8 multiplexed FBGs of 1mm in length and spaced at about 3 mm (Fig. 2). The polyimide coating in the FBG zone, plus a few mm on both ends of the zone, was removed with sulphuric acid to eliminate the effects of the coating and assure a strong bonding with the surrounding epoxy matrix. When the samples were cut out of the composite plate, care was taken to place the optical fiber in the middle of the beam.

Fig. 2: A schematic of an FBG wavelength multiplexed optical fiber [10].

It should be noted that the strain distribution around the delamination crack is highly non-homogeneous. [4]. However, due to the small gauge length of the FBG sensors, it was assumed (and verified with the numerical model, Sec 4) that over the length of the gauge (i.e., FBG length), the strain remains constant and the single peak shift was sufficient to obtain the strain at the corresponding location using Eq. (1). If this was not the case, a more elaborate technique based on Optical low coherence reflectometry (OLCR) should have been used to obtain a direct strain distribution along a short or a long FBG sensor [4].

2.2 Experimental methods

The 4ENF specimen, as shown schematically in Fig. 3, was used to study Mode II delamination of the composite. An advantage of the 4ENF test is the

long zone of stable crack propagation [11]. Indeed,

crack on one end. To ensure that all four loading

Fig. 3: A schematic of the 4ENF testing configuration indicating the two types of support on the left-hand side and the location of the optical fiber on the tensile part of the specimen (see text for details).

as long as the crack tip is between the two upper rollers ((B) and (D) in Fig. 3), the propagation is stable. When it approaches roller (D) the crack is arrested.

pins are subjected to the same load, the steel beam holding the two upper pins (B) and (D) was allowed to rotate at point (C) around an axis in the width direction of the sample. The spans of the test were chosen so that the upper span $L=80$ mm was half that of the lower span $2L = 160$ mm. The samples were placed in such a way that the initial crack tip was between the loading pins (B) and (D) and for those equipped with a sensor, the end of the FBG zone was 10mm away from loading pin (D) in order to avoid the pin's influence on the measured signal. The crack length was measured from the centre of the lower left pin (A) to the crack tip as determined by the graduation lines on the specimen side.

Fig. 4: The standard 'pin' and frictionless 'roller' 4ENF setups.

This stable propagation enables monitoring of the propagating crack and strain measurements with the embedded FBG sensor. Two different test setups were used in this work: In the first, subsequently called *pin-setup*, the load was applied onto the sample (at points (A), (B), (D) and (E)) by 10 mm diameter steel loading pins placed in a v-notch and held in place by springs (Fig. 4). In the second setup, called *roller-setup*, the pins were supported by roller bearings. In this latter setup the friction between the load pins and the composite is practically eliminated (loading point (A) is further described below). Photographs of the two fixtures are shown in Fig. 4.

During several pilot tests, with the pin-setup, it was observed that the samples were horizontally displaced due to the unequal stiffness. Since the crack length was measured with the graduation drawn on the sample, such a shift would lead to erroneous crack length data. To avoid this displacement, the samples were blocked at pin (A). For the pin-setup, the pin was cut two millimetres above the centre and glued to the sample (see Figs. 3 and 4). The loading pin (E) was reduced to a diameter of 7 mm to account for the reduced height of the cut pin (A). In the case of the roller-setup, the pin (A) was replaced by a triangular prism which was supported by roller bearings. The sample was blocked in the support by a triangular groove machined on the cylinder (see Fig. 4).

The stiffness in a 4ENF sample is not uniform along the sample length because of the presence of the

All samples were loaded with a rate of 0.04mm/s until the first crack initiation occurred. Initiation consisted of a sudden jump attributed to the resin

rich zone just behind the PTFE insert. In the case of the pin-setup, an initial long crack growth jump was observed accompanied by a load reduction. Thus, the sample was unloaded and then reloaded to initiate the crack and obtain an initiation value of G_{IIc} . For the roller-setup a steadily growing crack was observed after the jump therefore, the sample was not unloaded. All samples were loaded until the crack reached the loading pin (D). During the entire crack propagation photographs were taken every two seconds with a CCD camera to monitor crack length. The time for the crack to cross a marking on the side of the sample was extracted from these images and correlated with the corresponding load and displacement. A linear fit of the compliance versus crack length curve was then carried out in order to calculate the crack length for the complete load displacement curve and also calculate the ERR.

2.3 Strain measurements

The wavelengths of the FBG sensors were measured with a SM130 device from Micron Optics™ at an acquisition rate of 100 Hz throughout the test. The sensor consisted of an array of eight FBGs with a separation, in reflection wavelengths, of 5nm which guaranteed that the reflection peaks wouldn't superimpose when they shift during the test. The measured wavelength changes were transformed into strain using the Bragg relation (1) [12]:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{Bi}}{\lambda_{B0,i}} = (1 - p_e)\varepsilon_{z,i} \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda_{B0,i}$ is the Bragg wavelength of each FBG ($i=1, \dots, 8$), and $\Delta\lambda_{Bi}$ is the corresponding peak shift due to strain $\varepsilon_{z,i}$. The effective photoelastic coefficient p_e is a property of the fiber equal to 0.2148. It can be calculated on the basis of the Pockel's constants and the Poisson's ratio of the fiber [12,13] or measured experimentally by loading a single sensor and using Eq. (1).

4. Numerical modeling

Stress analysis of the crack fiber interaction on a double cantilever beam specimen made of the same material, with the optical fiber at the same location as in the present studies, showed negligible influence on the ERR and load-displacement curves in Mode I delamination [6]. Thus, a two dimensional

plane strain analysis is a realistic approximation and the measured and calculated quantities in the present studies are considered to not be influenced by the present of the optical fiber near the delamination plane. Accordingly, the numerical model used to simulate the 4ENF tests consisted of two beams each one with 8700 linear plane strain brick elements (Abaqus CPE4R).

The cohesive zone approach is a convenient numerical tool in modeling crack propagation at the interface of similar or dissimilar materials like adhesive joints and composite layers [14,15]. In this method, the pertinent material properties, such as fracture energy and fracture strength, are taken into account directly in a damage mechanics based model representing the evolution of the interfacial stresses as a function of the opening displacements and accumulated damage.

Among different cohesive element constitutive relations, the bilinear traction-separation model, shown in Fig. 5, was employed in this study, because of its simplicity, with the maximum stress criterion for damage initiation on the cohesive elements. According to the model, initially, the cohesive traction increases linearly with a slope of K . Once the traction in the cohesive zone reaches a certain value τ_{max} , damage initiation takes place. Upon further loading, evolution of damage from initiation to complete failure is defined based on the energy dissipated due to damage process. This energy is identified as fracture energy equal to the area under the traction-separation curve of denoted as G_{IIc} (Fig.5). To use a cohesive zone in the simulation, the initial stiffness K , damage initiation stress τ_{max} and Mode II fracture energy G_{IIc} should be identified. Note that K should be sufficiently high to minimize its effect on the overall compliance of the model. Regarding τ_{max} and G_{IIc} , they were numerically identified in order to simulate the applied load and the strains on the FBG sensor.

The interface between the two beams was modeled using cohesive elements of 20 μ m length and zero thickness. In this way the fracture surfaces were in contact with each other right from the beginning of the simulation. From the loading pin (D), to the right hand end of the specimen, the beams were tied together without cohesive elements in between. The

loading pins (B), (D), and (E) were simulated as analytical surfaces.

Fig. 5: Traction-separation law of the cohesive zone model used in the present studies.

Hard contact was defined between the fracture surfaces to avoid interpenetration of the two arms as well as between the pins and the specimen. Two friction coefficients μ_c and μ_s were defined, for the contact between cracked surfaces and the contact between pins and specimen, respectively, and a maximum of $5\mu\text{m}$ of elastic slip was assumed. The load was introduced by displacing point (C) which was situated 40mm above the sample and coupled to the loading pins (B) and (D). To ensure that only shear stresses introduce damage, the criterion for the other two directions was set to 1000MPa. The cohesive element stiffness was chosen to be 98000GPa/mm in the normal direction of the cohesive elements and 6000GPa/mm in shear. The maximum stress at damage initiation as well as the energy of the damage and external friction coefficients were identified with an inverse identification algorithm using the strain distribution around the crack (measured with the FBGs) and the applied load and displacements as target values. Moreover, a parametric study in which both friction coefficients were varied was carried out to elucidate the effects of friction on the load-response and energy dissipation mechanisms in 4ENF tests.

In order to identify the parameters of the cohesive elements along the interface in the presence of friction, the experimentally obtained strain distribution ε_{exp} (measured by FBGs, see Fig. 6) and load-displacement values P_{exp} were compared to the ones provided by the numerical simulations, ε_{num} and P_{num} . Thus, these parameters were implemented in an error measure defined as:

$$F(\tau_{max}, G_{IIc}, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{P_{num} - P_{exp}}{P_{exp}} \right]^2 + \frac{1}{2n_{fbg}} \left\| \frac{\varepsilon_{num} - \varepsilon_{exp}}{\varepsilon_{exp}} \right\|^2 \quad (2)$$

where n_{fbg} is the sensor number on the wavelength multiplexed optical fiber. The error norm $F(\tau_{max}, G_{IIc}, \mu)$ was then employed as an objective function which was minimized iteratively using the *lsqnonlin* non-linear least-square solver built in the commercial software Matlab® v7.7. At each iteration, an FE solution for P_{num} and ε_{num} was performed for the current set of identification parameters τ_{max} , G_{IIc} and μ using Abaqus® v6.10 and when required the derivatives of the solution were evaluated by finite difference. Convergence of the minimization algorithm was monitored and a repeatability analysis was performed to verify that the final solution did not depend on the initial set of the parameters. It should be noted that fiber bridging was not considered in the cohesive model since it was observed that the FE model prediction without bridging matched already very well the experimentally determined strain distribution (Fig. 6).

5. Results and discussion

5.1 Strain distribution around the crack tip:

Combining the *strain – time* data obtained from the FBG measurements with the *crack length – time* data from the visual crack length measurements (using compliance to get quasi continuous data points in the latter), time was eliminated and a *strain - crack length* plot was obtained for each for each FBG.

Additionally, since the position of each FBG within the sample is known from OLCR [5,16] measurements, these curves can be shifted to a common origin. In this work the position of the last FBG sensors was taken as a reference and all the other strain curves are transferred to this position. At this position, the crack tip was set as the zero as shown in Fig. 6. Note here that after the shift, the feature which was characteristic for the crack tip, namely a dramatic increase in strain ahead of the crack tip and practically zero strains in the wake of the crack. In addition, all curves practically coincide indicating a self-similar evolution of the strain profile. Note that in a previous work on Mode I delamination [4,5] changes in the individual strain

profiles were observed indicating toughening mechanisms, in particular fiber bridging with a significant increase in the ERR.

Fig. 6: Axial strain data measured with the embedded sensors. Note here the difference in the wake of the crack. Ahead of the crack the curves practically superimpose.

The first FBG in the array (in the direction of the crack advance) thus give most of the information from the zone behind the crack tip whereas the last one provides the information from the zone ahead of the crack tip.

Fig. 7: Measured and simulated load-displacement curves for both 4ENF setups.

Note that if the fiber is embedded in the upper half of the sample the exact same strain distribution with reversed signs is observed.

Load –Displacement curves: Figure 7 displays the load displacement curves of the 4ENF tests. The initial parts show the linear elastic behaviour of the material in both setups. Upon initiation the crack jumps for several millimeters which is due to the

resin rich zone at the insert's tip. Then, there is a clear difference between the two set-ups: the load decreases rapidly and with intermittent jumps for the pin setup, while it is slightly increasing and not showing any jumps for the roller-setup. Towards the end of the propagation, the load slightly increases in both setups which is due to the crack interaction with the second upper pin (D).

Energy release rate data are shown in Fig. 8. These curves were obtained using the derivative of a (linear) compliance versus crack length fit to calculate G_{II} (note that the linear fit has an R^2 of >0.98) according to Eq. (3) :

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 8: Energy release rate data for the two types of support (The dotted lines are from the pin-setup and solid lines are from the roller-setup).

As the strain distribution measured with the FBG sensors has shown, there was no fibre bridging (or if it is present it is independent of crack length and can thus not be responsible for a change in ERR). This is also confirmed by visual inspection of the fracture surfaces where no bridging fibres were observed after delamination. However, another dissipation mechanism that is clearly present in Mode II delamination is friction. Two different locations of friction can be identified: friction between the loading pins and the sample surface and friction between the fracture surfaces. The experiments have shown that the pin to sample surface friction plays an important role as the change in this friction

resulted in dramatically different test behaviour. The contribution of the friction of the fracture surfaces was further studied in a numerical model that allowed to examine individually the influence of each of these two friction sources on the 4ENF test.

Simulations with cohesive elements: First, the parameters of the cohesive elements and the coefficient for the friction between the pin and the sample surface were identified with a parametric FE-model of the pin-setup. An inverse identification algorithm was used where the objective function was an error vector constructed from the difference between the strain distribution measured with the FBG sensors and the simulated strain. The minimization of the error gave a value of $\tau_{max} = 38$ MPa for the damage initiation criterion and the friction between the pins and the sample surface was found to be $\mu_s=0.35$. The ERR was identified to be $G_{IIC} = 1070$ J/m². From the results in Fig. 8 it is immediately clear that this value cannot be obtained from the load displacement curve measured with the pin-setup, however, it corresponds very well to the ERR measured with the roller-setup.

Next, the influence of the friction between the fracture surfaces was studied. This parameter did not converge in the identification. Thus it was varied manually between 0.04 and 0.3 keeping all other parameters unchanged. Figure 9 (a) shows that there is almost no change in the load displacement curves upon varying this friction parameter. On the other hand, the change of the pin to surface friction results in a significant change of the load displacement curve as shown in Fig. 9b. As the friction of the fracture surfaces leads to a change of dissipated energy, the load changes slightly and it was found that a friction of $\mu_c = 0.2$ leads to the best fit between the measured and simulated load displacement curves, however, this parameter has almost no importance on the simulation results.

A comparison of the load displacement curves from the experiments and the corresponding simulations with the identified parameters (the pin to surface friction was put to zero for the roller setup simulation) is shown in Fig. 7. The length of the initial crack a_0 was taken after the first jump as the numerical model did not simulate the resin rich region and the resulting jump of the load. Thus, the

initial linear increase does not overlap between the experiment and the simulation. The rest of the two curves are well validated by the experimental curves. These two numerical models show clearly that the friction between the pin and the sample surface ($\mu_s = 0.35$ for the pin-setup and $\mu_s = 0$ for the roller setup) is the single most important difference between the two setups. Further, this friction also explains the discrepancy between the identified ERR and the ERR found experimentally with the pin-setup as well as its decreasing nature on the latter setup.

Fig. 9: Simulated load-displacement curve for different friction coefficients, (a) the composite – composite friction μ_c is varied and the support friction is $\mu_s = 0.35$, (b) the support friction μ_s is

varied and the composite – composite friction is $\mu_c=0.2$.

Conclusions

1. The two types of support used in the present studies of Mode II delamination testing clearly demonstrate the importance of friction of the load-displacement curves and energy release data.
2. The axial strain distribution during a Mode II delamination cracking was measured with an embedded wavelength multiplexed FBG sensor. The strain profiles from the FBG sensors superimpose well demonstrating the absence of fiber bridging during crack growth.
3. The strain distribution was used to identify the parameters of a cohesive element model including damage initiation and ERR as well as friction parameters. The numerical models with the identified parameters reproduced very well the experimental curves.

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